

ARTISTIC LITERATURE AS A MEANS OF FORMING THE LITERACY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11466312>

Abstract. The article talks about the fact that the formation of literacy of children of preschool age with the help of fiction is an important tool.

Keywords. Fiction, mental, moral and aesthetic education, intellectual abilities, perception, development of speech activity, speech culture, synthesis of human feelings.

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Annotation . V state govoritsya, chto formirovanie gramotnosti detey doshkolnogo vozrasta s pomoshchyu chudojestvennoy literatury yavlyaetsya vajnym instrumentom.

Key words . X udozhestvennaya literature , umstvennoe , nravstvennoe i aesthetic educational , intellectual ability , perception , development rechevoy deyatelnosti , culture rechi , synthesis chuvstv human

, there is a contradiction between increasing the interest of preschool children in works of art, developing a social procedure for the implementation of close familiarization with them, and insufficient organization of methodological support for this process. it is known. Pedagogical needs of solving the problems of introducing children to works of art are to create a system aimed at forming the ethical and aesthetic attitude of the preschool child to the surrounding world through these literatures and to enrich it with the content.

The leading features of the literary text, the artistic elements that lead children to spiritual perfection, the main idea, leading idea and artistic power of the work have been shortened. As a result a dry, informational or instructional text appeared, which means that today's young learners are more educated and smarter than the authors of these educational materials imagined at their age level.

Fiction is the main tool for intellectual, moral and aesthetic education of children. Along with the formation of a child's scientific worldview, fiction also has an impact on mental education. The mutual coordination of scientific outlook and mental education is the most leading principle in the development of mental education of students. Children's moral sense and standards of behavior are formed through fiction. Fiction as a means of aesthetic education expresses the ability to feel beauty, use one's creative potential, and form a positive attitude towards nature and social relations in society. This contributes to the education of the aesthetic perception of students.

During the perception of fiction books read by the teacher, the connection between the child's speech and aesthetic development is clearly visible, the language is mastered in its aesthetic function. Possession of figurative and expressive means of language serves the

development of artistic perception of a literary work. Through works of art, wonderful examples of literary language quickly enter the learner's mind, especially in stories, children learn conciseness and clarity of language; and through poems, they feel the musicality and melodiousness of Uzbek speech, and through the clear plot and expressiveness of fairy tales, they get a close understanding of its meaning.

The uniqueness of fiction is that it gives children pleasure, activates all their highest abilities and powers, encourages them to be creative. This is the creative task of fiction. However, creative activity involves the communication of a person with other people, the desire to create something for others. Here, the heuristic (creativity) function intersects with the communicative function, as a result of which fiction works as a means of communication between adults and children, children's community.

Communication serves as the main mediator in the implementation of the social and organizational function of fiction. Communication brings children closer to their peers, loved ones, family and community members. It is through communication that the function of socialization of the individual is realized, and fiction contributes as a unique resource connecting the individual with the society. Purposeful actions to ensure the socialization of the person ensure the effectiveness of the educational process. As a result of ensuring the effectiveness of the socialization and educational function of fiction, the educational task based on interrelated cognitive value is realized.

Positive protagonists in fiction are very important for the formation of kindness and empathy in children. The emergence of a strong and stable interest in children's fiction helps to develop attention to what is said and read. The needs of the educational system in terms of working with preschool children have matured over time. Through the literature read at this age, it helps to synthesize human feelings and activate the desire to participate in the processes taking place around them. Children who experience different emotions with the main characters of the works pay attention to the mood of the people around them. In addition, kindness and honesty, honesty and civic responsibility are also brought up in children.

The child's inner world develops in the process of mastering works. Artistic language helps the child to receive all the sounds of the mother's speech, accelerates the process of aesthetic perception of the surrounding world, and helps to collect and strengthen moral ideas. Introduction to fiction is often done at an early stage with folklore miniatures - children's rhymes and songs. After that, children are introduced to folk tales. A deep level of humanity, a positive moral orientation, lively humor, richness of figurative language - these are the main features of all works. Fairy tales, stories and poems of the writer are presented to children. In pre-school educational organizations, children embody the characters of various fairy tales.

In the process of increasing students' love for art, the following tasks are performed.

1. To create the pace of the surrounding space in the child's mind and establish priority life values.
2. Arousing enthusiasm for works and books of various genres.
3. To explain the principles of the features of the literary text genre, to develop analytical skills in children.

4. Stimulating children's creative activity, holding role-playing games and plot dramatization, awarding winners. Learning to read expressively .

5. Improving literary speech.

6. Acquaintance with oral creativity and interest in it, improvement of perception of texts and formation of aesthetic taste.

In order to form a permanent passion for books in children and provide conditions for the use of literary experience, certain goals and tasks are set for each young student:

1. Creating a unified picture of the surrounding world in children's minds (to establish basic life values);

2. Formation and construction of literary speech (mastering the main elements of linguistic expressiveness by getting acquainted with the rich world of artistic genre);

3. Acquaintance with the world of literature (ensure progress in artistic perception of unity of form and content, increase interest in literature and form aesthetic taste).

In the formation of the fairy tale and story section of fiction, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

Considering children's need to study literature take a n hold a condition to create , teach to work independently in the field of literary education .

2. Raising the level of educators in ways to attract children to works of art.

3. Bolal a rning empty the time transfer new women 's , women 's forms study process and to education about I 'm sorry in the documents reflection delivered according to demand integration to do and others

In conclusion, the following qualities are formed as a result of the intersection of preschool children's interest in studying fiction and educators' desire to creatively organize this process: the formation of children's emotional response to social life events; perception and understanding of the content of the work; the emergence of a desire to sympathize with the joys and sorrows of others; constant search and striving for action; changing the way of life in didactic game activities aimed at understanding the content of the work; the desire to participate in work that can aesthetically decorate life; the need to act together, the ability to rejoice in the success of others, etc. It is these aspects that ensure the formation of the most important pedagogical and psychological knowledge, such as personal culture, spirituality, the basics of aesthetic education and worldview, through fiction literature.

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